

Manifesto for a responsible communication of science Campus Gutenberg

Peace is much more than the absence of violence. According to the United Nations, poverty, racism, environmental disasters, lack of democracy and the violation of human rights also threaten peace. Is the popularization of science communication helping the democratization of science, and is it making these problems more visible? What can we do, as people dedicated to communicating science, to actively contribute to peace with our work? A group of science communication professionals, in the context of Campus Gutenberg-CosmoCaixa 2022, have drafted the following manifest:

The undersigned make a call to action so that both the research we communicate and the way in which we communicate it:

1. Help improve society
2. Include those affected by it (give them a voice, involve them in the process and allow them to decide)
3. Are at the service of disadvantaged communities, especially the poorest
4. Are democratic and/or promote democracy
5. Respect and try to protect the environment
6. Defend human rights
7. Work effectively to achieve peace
8. Do not have conflicts of interest or declare them openly
9. Are accompanied by measures that try to avoid (or denounce) a misuse of its possible applications
10. Use language and visual resources that do not encourage violence in any way
11. Inform, with as much evidence as possible, about the potential future impacts of research and its possible applications
12. Take into account all people.

You can join the manifesto by filling in [this form](#).

The undersigned, thus, are committed to work hard for a science and a science communication that respects these values.

List of signatories

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About this manifesto

The authorship of this manifesto corresponds entirely to those who wrote and signed it.

The space in which the seed of this manifesto began was the [Campus Gutenberg-CosmoCaixa](#), in its 2022 edition. Since 2010, Campus Gutenberg-CosmoCaixa is a gathering of hundreds of science communication professionals, mainly from Spain. The event is co-organized by the Studies Center on Science, Communication and Society from Universitat Pompeu Fabra (CCS-UPF), the UPF-Barcelona School of Management (UPF-BSM) and "laCaixa" Foundation. The Associació Catalana de Comunicació Científica (ACCC), Asociación Española de Comunicación Científica (AEC2) and Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología (FECYT) also collaborate in Campus Gutenberg-CosmoCaixa.